

COLLABORATIVE DIGITAL PRESERVATION POLICY REVISION AT THE NATIONAL LIBRARY AND ARCHIVES NEW ZEALAND

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Abstract – In 2024, the National Library of New Zealand and Archives New Zealand convened the Digital Preservation Policy Revision Working Group. The goal of this group, whose membership spanned both institutions, was to develop a new policy to replace the existing Joint Digital Preservation Strategy, published in 2011. This poster will present the resulting 2025 Digital Preservation Policy, outline the steps undertaken by the working group to develop the policy, and identify the work needed to operationalize the policy.

A digital preservation policy is often one of the foundational documents of a successful digital preservation programme. The proposed poster, which will include information on the process of policy development, the resulting content, and the steps needed to operationalize the policy, will be a useful case study for other institutions that are considering developing or revising their digital preservation policy documents.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The National Library of New Zealand Te Puna Mātauranga o Aotearoa and Archives New Zealand Te Rua Mahara o te Kāwanatanga have a long history of collaborative digital preservation. This includes shared digital preservation infrastructure and a joint Digital Preservation Strategy published in 2011[1].

In 2024, the National Library of New Zealand and Archives New Zealand convened the Digital Preservation Policy Revision Working Group, whose goal was to develop a new policy to replace the outdated document and could serve as a foundation for the ongoing work for each organisation. The development of the 2025 Digital Preservation Policy, including a summary of the activities of the working group in 2024-2025, the resulting policy document, and the remaining steps to operationalize the policy, can provide a useful case study for other organisations that are considering new policy development or revision to existing policy documents.

II. POLICY DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

The formal development of the digital preservation policy began with the convening of the Digital Preservation Policy Revision Working Group in 2024. This group included representatives from both the National Library and Archives New Zealand, and from across business units within both organisations that were responsible for managing or creating digital content. Their role was to provide subject matter expertise on the policy and how it may impact their respective operational work. The drafting of the policy document was primarily the work of the Digital Preservation Policy and Outreach Specialist, who was also the chair of the working group and facilitator for all working group meetings.

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The working group met regularly for a period of six months in 2024. Each session was organized around a policy component identified in the Digital Preservation Coalition's *Digital Preservation Policy Toolkit Template* [2]. The group first reviewed a description of each policy component and its context in a broader digital preservation policy, along with the corresponding passage of the original 2011 Joint Digital Preservation Strategy. The group then discussed examples of similar policy components from cultural heritage institutions around the world.

This collaborative, discussion-based process allowed the group to identify themes and establish common preferences across its membership. This guidance was captured in meeting notes and formed the initial drafting of the policy, which was circulated back through the working group for comments and revisions. Working group members reported back regularly to their business units on the progress of the policy and solicited feedback to ensure broad organizational alignment and awareness of the document's progress.

III. POLICY PRINCIPLES

One of the key outcomes of the 2025 Digital Preservation Policy was to articulate a new set of policy principles to guide digital preservation activities across each institution. It was important to the group to identify principles that tied directly to operational work, but were also expressed in a way that enabled their continuing relevance in the face of technological or organisational changes over time. The resulting principles are:

- 1) We protect and preserve the digital information in our care.
- 2) We have a lifecycle approach to digital preservation.
- 3) We are leaders in digital preservation in Aotearoa New Zealand, Australasia, and the Pacific.
- 4) We operate a sustainable digital preservation programme through careful financial stewardship, organizational planning, and close consideration of the environmental impact of our work.
- 5) Our digital preservation work supports our responsibilities under Te Tiriti o Waitangi.
- 6) We recognize that preserving digital information is intrinsically linked with enabling appropriate access, in alignment

with current legislation, access restrictions, and treaty obligations.

These policy principles reflect the deep involvement of stakeholders across each institution, and a shared commitment to good digital preservation practices that are repeatable, sustainable, and aligned with institutional resources and capabilities.

IV. NEXT STEPS

The next major milestone for the Digital Preservation Policy will be formal approval within each organization. Following approval, the policy will be owned by the Digital Preservation Team, of which both National Library and Archives New Zealand staff are members. This team will also be responsible for any operational changes that will result from the policy.

V. CONCLUSION

A digital preservation policy is often an integral part of a successful digital preservation programme. In order to be useful and meaningful, such policies must align with operational processes and provide guidance for future decision making. The example of the collaborative policy revision approach taken by the National Library and Archives New Zealand can serve as a case study for organisations that are considering development or revision of their own digital preservation policies.

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AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

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